

ISOLATION OF CURCUMIN EXTRACT FROM CURCUMA LONGA

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Curcumin, a polyphenol of yellow crystals with that gives turmeric its yellow color, it is extracted from the rhizome of turmeric. It belongs to the perennial herb named *Curcuma longa* L.

Keywords: *Curcuma longa*, curcumin, turmeric, soxhlet extraction.

Purpose of the study: This research aims to extract the bioactive compound, curcumin from the contents of *Curcuma Longa*. And in its analysis 'Learning is the purpose of research.

Efficacy: *Curcuma Longa* has been used as antiseptic, wound healing, and anti-inflammatory agent. Diabetes can be efficiently treated with curcumin by increasing insulin resistance. And it has antibacterial and anticancer properties.

Materials and methods: Extraction was carried out using a soxhlet apparatus consisting of a distillation flask, a rack holder, and a condenser. The *Curcuma Longa* plant was crushed and packed in filter paper and placed in a rack holder in contact with fresh solvent condensed from the distillation flask. Curcumin extraction occurs in the upper chamber of the desiccator. During extraction, 50 mL of ethanol was used as a solvent for 2 g of *Curcuma Longa* powder. The extraction process was carried out at 78 °C for 8 hours. The mass of the isolated extract was 2.55 mg/g. The extract containing curcumin, which is considered a biologically active substance, was analyzed using the IR spectroscopic analysis method. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. IR spectrum of curcumin extracted from *Curcuma Longa* plant

According to the results of the obtained IR spectrum, the (OH) groups have a stretching vibration at 3200-3500 cm^{-1} , a C=C aromatic stretching vibration at 1427 cm^{-1} , and a high intensity range of mixed vibrations at 1512 cm^{-1} , including that it was found to be associated with extended carbonyl bond vibrations, and the presence of the flavonoid curcumin in the extract was investigated.

Conclusion: Curcumin had been extracted from *Curcuma longa* through soxhlet extraction. The extraction products were then analyzed using physicochemical methods, results of the analysis were compared with the documentary standard, and it was learned that this plant contains biologically active curcumin.

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